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How malleable is the aversion to stigmatized work?

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ABSTRACT

Conflicting narratives about controversial business models are common in the debates surrounding stigmatized companies. We study whether such narratives affect individuals' willingness to accept stigmatized work. In a laboratory experiment, we show that reservation wages for a job which assists the marketing of tobacco products are substantially higher than for a similar but non-stigmatized job. We then randomly expose participants either to narratives commonly used by the tobacco industry or to narratives used by a civil society opponent of the tobacco industry. Neither set of narratives affects behavior. This finding can be explained by the firm moral views held by participants. Our results suggest that aversion to stigmatized work is a robust feature of preferences, which is necessary for moral concerns to persistently influence labor market outcomes.

1. Introduction

Many companies are perceived to have fundamental moral flaws that discredit them (Hudson, 2008). Examples of such stigmatized companies include corporations active in the tobacco, arms and gambling industries (Schneider et al., 2025, forthcoming), producers of genetically modified crops (Schurman, 2004), operators of nuclear power plants (Kitschelt, 1986) and firms in the apparel industry that employ sweatshops (Harrison and Scorse, 2010). Corporate stigma imposes non-monetary costs on employees by undermining both their self-image and their social reputation (Ashraf and Bandiera, 2017; Dur and van Lent, 2018). These "moral costs" have the potential to substantially affect market outcomes. For example, theories of compensating wage differentials predict that current and prospective employees will require financial compensation to engage in stigmatized work, which in turn reduces labor supply and drives up market wages (Frank, 1996; Schneider et al., 2025, forthcoming).¹ However, for the aversion to stigmatized work to persistently influence market outcomes, these preferences must endure in market environments.

There are good reasons to question the importance and stability of moral concerns in markets (Levitt and List 2007, Levitt and List, 2008; Falk and Szech, 2013), and many scholars have argued that the nature of markets may erode such moral considerations (e.g., Bowles 1998, Sandel 2012). In the context of stigmatized work, moral concerns may be particularly weakened because workers are often exposed to narratives that justify participation in this type of work. Indeed, stigmatized companies often use media campaigns

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¹ Despite paying high wages, major companies deem difficulties in recruitment due to their industry's image as an important enough risk to see its disclosure to regulators and shareholders as required (British American Tobacco, 2015, p. 37; Philip Morris International Inc., 2015, p. 14). Another consequence of these non-monetary costs can be decreased employee effort (Ariely, Bracha and Meier, 2009; Carpenter and Gong, 2016).

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that furnish justifications and excuses for their controversial business model in attempts to improve their public image (Elsbach, 1994; McDonnell and King, 2013).² These narratives might enable workers to use cognitive tactics to accept well-paid stigmatized work while maintaining a positive self-image (Bénabou, 2013; Bénabou, Falk and Tirole, 2020), thereby decreasing the aversion to stigmatized work.³ This form of motivated reasoning is, for example, reflected in the admission of a former tobacco trial lawyer: “I rationalized and denied, because the money was so good and because I could always rationalize it. That’s how you make a living, by rationalizing that black is not black, it’s white, it’s green, it’s yellow” (Rosenblatt, 1994). Consequently, aversion to stigmatized work may have only a limited impact on labor markets. On the other hand, by the time workers enter the labor market, they have often been exposed to extensive information about corporations in controversial fields and may hold firm moral views that are difficult to alter.⁴

In this paper, we study whether aversion to stigmatized work is malleable to persuasion attempts through narratives used in corporate image campaigns. Investigating this question is challenging because corporate image campaigns typically arise endogenously, as companies respond to political events or incidents, which makes causal identification difficult. A further identification challenge is that social movements and civil society organizations simultaneously use media campaigns to tarnish stigmatized companies’ reputations by persuading the public that these companies are behaving unacceptably and unethically (Schurman, 2004; King, 2008; Harrison and Scorse, 2010). This paper uses a laboratory experiment to address this identification challenge. The laboratory also allows us to measure labor supply for a broad range of wages. A limitation of this approach, however, is that we can only examine the effects of relatively short-term image interventions.⁵ In the experiment, subjects are offered a job that aids the marketing of cigarettes to young adults benefitting a stigmatized Fortune Global 500 corporation. Note that the corporation recruits students at the two universities from which we draw our subjects.

We first compare the labor supply for such a stigmatized job to the labor supply for a similar but non-stigmatized job. The stigmatized job represents a cigarettes marketing job benefitting a big tobacco company. The job consists of gift-wrapping three cigarettes and place them into the gift bag, which will then be distributed to smokers.⁶ The neutral job is similar to the stigmatized job. The only difference is that subjects have to wrap three pens, produced by an office supply company, in gift-wrap paper. The pens are white, not sharpened, and have similar dimensions as the cigarettes (8.5×0.7 cm). As a result, the effort costs of doing the neutral job are similar to those of doing the stigmatized job. To induce social image concerns, which is an important feature of labor markets outside the laboratory, subjects’ decisions to accept or decline the job are publicly observed by all other participants.

We find a causal and large impact of work stigmatization on labor supply. The average reservation wage for the stigmatized job is estimated to be more than nine times as large as for the non-stigmatized job. 20 % of subjects decline to do the stigmatized job for even the maximum wage offered, \$25—for a job that requires no more than 5 minutes. These findings provide evidence that many employees are indeed willing to forgo substantial financial gains to avoid stigmatized work.

We then study the malleability of the aversion to stigmatized work by randomly exposing participants to one of two videos that include narratives in support or against the tobacco company’s business model. Both videos used in the experiment are actual corporate image media employed by leading players in the debate surrounding tobacco. The *positive intervention* video is created by the tobacco corporation which manufactures the cigarettes used in the stigmatized job. The video targets university graduates as potential recruits. It includes different potential justifications and excuses for the company’s business model. For example, the video argues that the company provides its customers with information to help them make informed choices. The *negative intervention* is a video jointly produced by the American Cancer Society and the World Lung Foundation. It shows the suffering caused by tobacco, attacks the tobacco industry for its business practices, and makes appeals to the viewer to help fight the tobacco industry. We choose these interventions as two large, well-funded organizations in the tobacco debate had them made. Both videos are professionally produced, emotionally appealing and provide a plethora of arguments in favor of their positions. Subjects report their reservation wages immediately after viewing the video.

We find that neither medium has an effect on reservation wages. The treatment effects are small and not statistically significant. Moreover, the treatment conditions have no statistically significant effect on the stated willingness to accept employment with the

² Corporations with environmentally harmful business practices, for example, use “greenwashing.” They mislead the public about their environmental behavior, or engage in selective disclosure to manage their public image (Marquis et al., 2016). In the case of the tobacco industry, internal company documents (World Health Organization, 2004), now public due to court order, show that tobacco companies have internal corporate image campaigns with an express purpose of improving employee morale and recruitment (British American Tobacco, 1998, p. 2; Philip Morris International Inc., 1999). Two examples of narratives that justify the business practices in the tobacco industry taken from a recruitment booklet are that “there is nothing in cigarettes that removes the ability of someone to stop smoking,” and that adults have a fundamental right to make their own fully informed consumption choices (British American Tobacco, 1999).

³ A recent and rapidly growing body of literature examines how narratives can be used more broadly for persuasion (e.g., Schwartzstein and Sunderam, 2021; Aina, 2024; Aina et al., 2024; Ambuehl et al., 2024; Barron and Fries, 2024).

⁴ Prior research in other settings finds that providing excuses or justifications for selfish behavior can reduce moral concerns (e.g., Dana et al., 2007; Hamman et al., 2010; Exley, 2016; Gino et al., 2016; Grossman and van der Weele, 2017; Hillenbrand and Verrina, 2022). Conversely, moral suasion can promote moral behavior (e.g., Mazar et al., 2008; Pruckner and Sausgruber, 2013; Ito et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2023); however, its effects can be weak and short-lived (e.g., Dal Bó and Dal Bó, 2014; Dwenger et al., 2016; Bott et al., 2020; Serra-Garcia and Szech, 2022).

⁵ Our interventions closely reflect persuasion efforts typically seen in recruitment contexts; notably, we use the official recruitment video of a tobacco company. However, in some settings, such as among long-term employees, individuals may experience exposure to image interventions over extended periods. Our study does not address the potential effects of such long-term exposure.

⁶ To ensure the study caused no harm, gift bags and cigarettes were only given to young adults who were regular smokers. From each gift bag recipient, we first bought four cigarettes. Thus, each participating young adult smoker ended up with either four or one fewer cigarettes.

tobacco company. We also elicit the moral perception of the stigmatized work, which allows us to shed some light on the reasons why the corporate image media have no effect: our measures indicate that participants have firm preexisting moral convictions regarding aiding marketing of the tobacco product; the company video neither affects the normative view of accepting employment for the tobacco company nor the beliefs about the social appropriateness of doing the job in the laboratory. The video by the American Cancer Society has no statistically significant effect on the normative view of working for the tobacco company, but does negatively affect the perceived social appropriateness of doing the job. However, the effect is small, which may explain why the video has no detectable effect on labor supply.

To further understand why corporate image media had no impact on labor supply, we conducted an additional online experiment to study the participants' perceptions of the videos and their impact on views of the tobacco industry. The company video successfully shifted some beliefs about the tobacco industry—such as its benefits to farmers and its research into less harmful products—but it had no effect on normative views about accepting employment for the tobacco company or labor supply. Moreover, the video was widely perceived as insincere and inaccurate. These findings suggest that the corporate media may provide those willing to accept stigmatized work with additional justifications, but this influence does not extend to changing broader normative perceptions. Conversely, the video by the American Cancer Society was perceived as sincere and accurate but had only a modest impact on perceptions of the tobacco industry and normative views about working for the tobacco company. Overall, these findings suggest that individuals entering the labor market often hold firm moral views that are difficult to change.

Our findings contribute to three literatures. First, it contributes to a literature that studies whether the impacts of moral concerns may be mitigated in market contexts (Dufwenberg, et al., 2011; Falk and Szech, 2013; Bartling, Weber and Yao, 2015; Kirchler, Huber, Stefan and Sutter, 2016; Schneider et al., 2023; Ziegler, Romagnoli and Offerman, 2024). The most related papers within this literature study labor market outcomes for stigmatized work. Prior work has shown that work stigmatization is correlated with higher wages (Frank, 1996; Moffatt and Peters, 2004; Arunachalam and Shah, 2008). To investigate whether this relationship is causal, Schneider, Brun and Weber (2025, forthcoming) implement a laboratory labor market for jobs as financial advisers who have a severe conflict of interest. They find that the aversion to stigmatized work leads to a decrease in labor supply and higher wages. Similarly, Cohn and Stoop (2025, forthcoming) provide evidence of reduced labor supply in the context of jobs involving the production of false COVID-19 information. However, existing studies overlook that in many real-world markets, workers and consumers are exposed to narratives crafted by stigmatized companies to justify their business model. Our contribution to this literature is to study the malleability of moral concerns in response to companies' attempts to influence individuals.⁷ If moral concerns are malleable, their impact on market outcomes—such as labor supply, wages, and consumer behavior—could be substantially reduced. By exposing participants to real corporate image media, we find that aversion to stigmatized work remains unaffected by these persuasion efforts. Overall, our results support the notion that the aversion to stigmatized work is a stable feature of preferences, which is necessary for moral concerns to persistently influence market outcomes.

Our finding that neither appeals to individuals' morality nor the provision of excuses and justifications for selfish behavior affect labor supply for stigmatized work also contributes to the understanding of the limits of moral suasion and self-serving belief manipulation (van der Weele et al., 2014; Ito et al., 2018; Ging-Jehli et al., 2020; Valero, 2020; Serra-Garcia and Szech, 2022). Bartling and Özdemir (2023) find that in contexts with strong social norms, people do not employ excuses to engage in immoral behavior. Similarly, in our study where the data on normative views suggest that people, at the time they enter the labor market, have strong views on tobacco, behavior is unaffected by the justifications and excuses provided by the corporate image campaigns.

Finally, recruitment and motivation in mission-oriented companies (such as public administration and nonprofits) are subject of a growing literature (e.g., Besley and Ghatak, 2005; Delfgaauw and Dur, 2007; Josse 2008; Tonin and Vlassopoulos, 2015; Cassar and Meier, 2018; Cassar, 2019). It studies the impact of pro-social corporate actions on worker motivation. Pro-social corporate actions are typically created in experiments by linking participants' effort choices with a donation to a charity. We differ from this work in that we explore the potential of impression management—a frequently used tool by employers (Akerlof, Matouschek and Rayo, 2020; Gibbons and Prusak, 2020)—as a tool for human resource management. Thus, unlike prior studies, we investigate a communicative strategy. We do not find an effect of impression management on labor supply, suggesting that the scope to change recruitment outcomes by means of image campaigns may be limited. A potential explanation for this finding is that participants see such image interventions as insincere, in line with Cassar and Meier (2021) who find that if employees perceive pro-social corporate actions as instrumentally rather than intrinsically motivated they are ineffective.

Our paper proceeds as follows: The next section outlines the design of the laboratory experiment. Section 3 presents the results. Section 4 details the design and findings of the complementary online study, and Section 5 concludes.

2. Study design

To study the impact of work stigmatization on labor supply, we elicit the labor supply for both a stigmatized job (the *stigmatized work condition*) and for a non-stigmatized job (the *neutral work condition*). Importantly, we vary only the degree to which work is stigmatized, while holding constant other job characteristics, in particular real-effort costs. With two additional treatment conditions,

⁷ Moreover, our setting differs in important dimensions: we look at a real-world stigmatized company, the task is palpably stigmatized, and the industry is tobacco rather than finance. Yet, like Schneider, Brun and Weber (2025, forthcoming), we find a large and causal wage premium for stigmatized work. A key strength of our experimental paradigm is that it allows for study of the impact of real-world corporate image media and narratives on labor supply.

the *positive intervention* and the *negative intervention*, we then study whether positive or negative corporate image interventions can alter the labor supply for stigmatized work. Table 1 provides an overview of the main distinctions among the four conditions.

In all conditions, working in the job is publicly observed by all other participants in the experimental session. This mirrors many labor markets outside the laboratory, where one's workplace is often observable.⁸ All participants in a session are assigned to the same treatment condition. Thus, all "observers" are fully aware of the moral nature of the job (Neutral or Stigmatized) and have been exposed to the same corporate image intervention. As a result, the image interventions can influence both the self-image and social image of the workers.

In the following, we first discuss the stigmatized and the neutral job. We then explain the image interventions, how we measure the labor supply and how we induce social image concerns. Finally, we discuss additional measures that we collect and explain the exact procedure of the experiment.

The stigmatized job. To study recruitment outcomes of stigmatized companies, subjects are offered a marketing job benefitting a big tobacco company.⁹ We employ a novel but simple job. On each participant's desk, there is a gift bag. The gift bag will be given to a young adult, regardless of the participant's choices. The participant is offered a job which consists of gift-wrapping three cigarettes and place them into the gift bag. Therefore, if the participant chooses to accept the job, she will cause a young adult to receive three cigarettes, otherwise, that young adult will not receive any cigarettes.¹⁰ To make sure that participants understand what the job entails, and what its consequences are, the following are placed on every participant's desk: the wrapping supplies (wrapping paper, stickers and ribbons), the gift bag, an example of a gift-wrapped cigarette, and a pack of cigarettes. The pack of cigarettes is an off-the-shelf pack of cigarettes with the manufacturer's name on it. All participants receive identical cigarette packs. This job has an industry analogue, working in marketing for the tobacco company.

The neutral job. The neutral job is similar to the stigmatized job. The only difference is that subjects have to wrap three pencils, produced by an office supply company, in gift-wrap paper. The pens are white, not sharpened and have similar dimensions as the cigarettes (8.5×0.7 cm). As a result, the real effort costs of doing the neutral job are similar to those of doing the stigmatized job.¹¹

Corporate image interventions. To study whether corporate image interventions influence labor supply, we show subjects in the positive and negative intervention conditions real-world videos designed to enhance, respectively diminish, corporate and industry image before we elicit labor supply.

In the positive intervention condition, the official company video of one of the world's leading tobacco companies is streamed to participants' computers.¹² This company is the manufacturer of the brand of cigarettes used in the job, and subjects are made aware of that fact. The video highlights what an attractive employer the tobacco corporation is, and how much working there means to its employees. Excuses and justifications are deployed throughout the video. Claims that can be seen as excuses or justifications include the statements that small farmers and their families in poor countries benefit from cultivating tobacco, that the company does not market to underage youth or children, that it provides its adult customers with information to help them make informed choices and that it conducts research to develop less harmful products. The video lasts four and a half minutes.

For the negative interventions condition, we use a video by what is presumably one of the world's leading opponent of the tobacco industry, the American Cancer Society (produced jointly with the World Lung Foundation).¹³ The video begins by asking how much a human life is worth. It then argues that for the tobacco industry one life is worth \$6000 as that is the profit made on average per person dying from smoking. The video explains that tobacco will kill one in every three children who takes up smoking, and that smoking is a cause of cancer, heart disease, lung disease, diabetes and other diseases. According to the video, six million people die due to smoking every year. The video explains that smoking can be stopped by taxing cigarettes, passing smoking bans, informing about the harms of smoking and *prohibiting "slick advertising and packaging."* The almost three-minute video concludes by directly addressing the viewer, saying that "we are the solution," and asking her to "fight back," and telling her "you can help."

In the stigmatized work and the neutral work conditions, subjects watch a neutral control video, a five-minute video that shows aerial footage of landscapes.¹⁴ The purpose of the control video is to make the stigmatized work condition as similar as possible to the intervention conditions.

Labor supply. After subjects have seen the respective video, we elicit their reservation wages for doing the job. To do so in an incentive compatible way, we use the mechanism developed by Becker et al. (1964). We use the multiple price list variant where

⁸ In some labor markets, workers can remain anonymous, particularly with the rise of remote work. Our estimated treatment effects represent an upper bound for such anonymous settings, where corporate media can only serve to protect a worker's self-image rather than their social image.

⁹ Employing this job has multiple advantages. First, the origin of the organizational stigma is seen by participants to be present in the job and the job is palpably stigmatized. Second, the job benefits a real-world stigmatized company. Third, both the positive and negative corporate image interventions produced by sophisticated organizations are available and suitable for use in the laboratory. Fourth, the job in the experiment is related to the corporate image interventions.

¹⁰ To ensure the study caused no harm, gift bags and cigarettes were only given to young adults who were regular smokers. From each gift bag recipient, we first bought four cigarettes. Thus, each participating young adult smoker ended up with either four or one fewer cigarettes. However, the participant's decisions influenced the final number of cigarettes the smokers retained.

¹¹ Indeed, there is no significant treatment difference in the time it takes subjects to wrap the objects (t-test, $t=0.81$, $p=0.420$; Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, $p=0.336$).

¹² We did not download the video, but participants streamed them from the official channels of the organization. The video can be seen on <https://www.gradcracker.com/hub/779/british-american-tobacco/videos/3285/we-are-bat-shining-the-spotlight-on-our-people-around-the-world>.

¹³ The video can be seen on the YouTube channel of the American Cancer Society, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2m7-z1a6-Es>.

¹⁴ The video can be seen on YouTube, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_9qZSKxbZdA.

Table 1
Overview of treatment conditions.

Treatment condition	Neutral work condition	Stigmatized work condition	Positive intervention condition	Negative intervention condition
Nature of Job	Neutral	Stigmatized	Stigmatized	Stigmatized
Corporate image intervention	Control	Control	Positive intervention	Negative intervention

participants are presented with a list of decisions. In our case, the list contains all integer wages from CHF 0 to CHF 25 (CHF 1 \approx USD 1). For each of these wages subjects choose whether they “accept” or “decline” the job. As they go down the list, subjects can switch between decline and accept as often as they like. If a subject accepts the job at one wage, and then switches to declining the job at a higher wage, we take this as an indicator that the subject failed to understand the choice situation. Participants also have the option to click a button to “decline to do the job for any wage,” which corresponded to selecting “decline” at each wage level.¹⁵ At the end of each experimental session, a single wage is randomly drawn for all participants in the session, and those who accepted the job at the drawn wage are required to complete the job.

Social image. Subjects’ decisions to accept or decline the job are publicly observed: At the end of each session, subjects’ pictures and their decisions for the wage that was drawn in that session are publicly displayed to all participants in that session. Each session has about eleven subjects. Subjects learn all of this before they make their choice. The pictures are taken at the beginning of the session, so the fact that behavior is publicly observed is salient.

Willingness to work for the tobacco company and moral perceptions. To investigate treatment effects on work preferences in labor markets outside the laboratory, we ask subjects to indicate on a five-point Likert scale how willing they are to work for each of 13 corporations on a list we give them, one of which is the tobacco company that produces the cigarettes and the video used in the experiment. Unlike the job of wrapping cigarettes, these job choices are hypothetical, but Wiswall and Zafar (2018) provide evidence that such stated preferences are predictive of actual, ultimate employment.

Moreover, in the stigmatized work and the intervention conditions, we elicit two measures of moral perception. First, we ask how moral the participant thinks it is to work for the tobacco industry (*normative view*). We ask this indirectly: “Imagine one of your fellow students starts working for [name of tobacco company] after finishing his/her studies. How moral do you think this is?” This question is designed to capture participants’ views on the morality of working for the tobacco company. Second, we measure participants’ views on the social appropriateness of accepting the job (*social appropriateness*). Participants are asked how socially appropriate they think it is to accept and to decline the stigmatized job for a wage of CHF 10. To measure social appropriateness in an incentive compatible way, we employ the method by Krupka and Weber (2013).

In addition, we ask subjects to what extent different motives play a role in deciding when to accept or decline the job. The motives offered relate to effort, ability, consequences, positive and negative externalities, and morals.¹⁶

Procedure and sample. The sequence of the experiment is as follows: upon arrival participants’ pictures are taken, and they then enter the lab where they find detailed written instructions on their desks. The instructions are reproduced in full in the online appendix. Then, they answer ten understanding questions about the study. Immediately after watching one of the three videos, they make their labor supply decisions. Subsequently, the additional measures are elicited, followed by a demographic questionnaire. Finally, the labor supply decisions of all participants are made public.

We calculated that to detect an effect of size (Cohen’s d) of 0.6 at the 5 percent level at a power of 80 percent, our study needs 60 subjects per condition. We conducted six sessions per condition, which resulted in 66 participants in the stigmatized work condition, 72 in the neutral work condition, 65 in the positive intervention condition, and 73 in the negative intervention condition, resulting in a total of 276 participants. We exclude two subjects with the non-monotone labor supply from our analysis.¹⁷

The experiment is programmed in z-Tree (Fischbacher, 2007). Participants were recruited using hroot (Bock, Baetge, and Nicklisch, 2014) from the joint subject pool of the University of Zurich and the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology between April and July 2018. Smokers were excluded from participation. Each session lasted about one hour. Average earnings were about CHF 34. Our study obtained ethical approval from the Human Subjects Committee of the Faculty of Economics, Business Administration, and Information Technology at the University of Zurich.

3. Results

The effect of work stigmatization on labor supply. Fig. 1 shows the labor supplies in all treatment conditions, including the

¹⁵ We included this option for individuals motivated by non-consequentialist moral concerns, where even considering a harmful job for any payoff can be viewed as immoral (e.g., Bénabou and Tirole, 2011). For example, a person with such motivations might avoid engaging with wage information from stigmatized companies and instead reject the idea of working there outright. We therefore added this option to decline the job at any wage to allow for these motivations.

¹⁶ To learn about subjects’ social preferences, we implement a moral trolley problem (Foot, 1967) and a dictator game with an endowment of \$2. Finally, we elicited subjects’ happiness (self-assessment manikin, Bradley and Lang, 1994). The online appendix provides the entire questionnaire.

¹⁷ These two subjects accepted the job at one wage and declined it at a higher wage. All other 274 subjects exhibit a monotone willingness to accept the job. The finding that almost all subjects exhibit monotone willingness to accept suggests that subjects understood the instructions and labor supply choice situation they were facing.

stigmatized work condition (dotted black line) and in the neutral work condition (solid green line). The labor supplies show the share of subjects that accept the respective job for each possible wage. In the neutral work condition, most participants (76.4 %) accept the job for a wage that is equal to or less than CHF 1, the lowest non-zero wage offered. All participants accept the neutral job for CHF 15. In contrast, in the stigmatized work condition, many subjects reject the job for substantial wages. 20 % of subjects even decline the stigmatized job for any of the wages offered, including the highest wage offered of CHF 25. Differences in labor supply are statistically significant at the 1 %-level (Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, $p < 0.001$).

Table 2 reports the results of regressions of reservation wages on an indicator variable of being in the stigmatized work condition.¹⁸ As our data is censored at CHF 26, we specify a Tobit model. The average reservation wage in the neutral work condition is CHF 0.92. The average reservation wage in the stigmatized work condition is estimated to be CHF 8.94 higher ($t = 5.14$, $p < 0.001$). Hence, we find a large causal impact of work stigmatization on labor supply. Appendix Tables A1 and A2 show that the results are similar when using a linear regression with robust standard errors instead of a Tobit model, and when analyzing the decision to decline the job at any wage rather than reservation wages.

Fig. 1 also reveals substantial heterogeneity in reservation wages for stigmatized work. While many subjects exhibit an aversion to accepting the stigmatized job, there is a substantial share (24 %) of workers that accept the job for less than CHF 1. In the next section, we investigate whether differences in moral perceptions explain the polarization of subjects' reservation wages for stigmatized work.

Moral perceptions and reservation wages for stigmatized work. Opinions regarding the morality of accepting jobs in the tobacco industry as well as performing the stigmatized job are polarized. While 42 % of subjects in the stigmatized work condition considers working for the cigarette manufacturer as immoral, 50 % of subjects have a neutral normative view. Furthermore, while 48 % of all subjects believe that it is at least somewhat socially inappropriate to accept the stigmatized job for a wage of CHF 10, 30 % of subjects think it is neither socially appropriate nor inappropriate.¹⁹

Could these divergent moral views explain the polarization of subjects' reservation wages? To look at this question, we estimate Tobit regression models of reservation wages on normative views and believed social appropriateness. As can be seen in Table 3, reservation wages reflect the perceived immorality of accepting the job. On average, a subject's reservation wage is estimated to be more than CHF 11 higher if she considers working for the cigarette manufacturer as "very immoral" rather than morally "neutral." Reservation wages are also higher for subjects who believe it is "socially very inappropriate" to accept the job in the lab compared to those subjects who consider this as "neither socially inappropriate nor socially appropriate." Results are similar for the two other treatment conditions that apply the stigmatized job, the positive intervention and negative intervention conditions (see Table A3 in the Appendix). Pooling the data from all three conditions, we find statistically significant coefficient estimates for both normative views and social appropriateness (see columns (5) and (6)).

These results show that it is the subjects who think accepting the job is immoral who demand a wage premium.

The effect of image interventions. The link between normative perceptions and labor supply suggests that changing a company's image might indeed influence labor supply. However, as Fig. 1 shows, neither the positive nor the negative intervention caused a substantial shift in labor supply. If anything, the positive intervention (i.e., the tobacco company video) appears to have slightly reduced labor supply for immoral work.

Table 2 gives the results of Tobit regressions of reservation wages on treatment condition dummies. We find no statistically significant effect of the positive intervention ($t = 0.96$, $p = 0.338$) or the negative intervention ($t = 1.22$, $p = 0.223$).²⁰ Estimates do not change substantially when controlling for gender, age and education (column 2). Substantially, the coefficient estimates are small.

For the positive intervention condition, we can reject a substantial positive impact on labor supply. The largest possible negative effect on reservation wages, according to the 95 % confidence interval, is CHF -1.82. This represents only 20.4 % of the "stigmatized work premium" of CHF 8.94, which is derived from comparing the stigmatized work condition with the neutral work condition. Thus, we conclude that aversion to stigmatized work cannot be easily mitigated by corporate image interventions.

For the negative intervention condition, the results are less clear. Although we observe no statistically significant effect, the largest possible positive effect on reservation wages, according to the 95 % confidence interval, is CHF 5.60—a non-negligible amount. While more research is needed, we cautiously interpret our findings to suggest that moral suasion may not be particularly effective in changing labor supply for stigmatized work.

Given the null effects on behavior, the question arises whether the image interventions are only unsuccessful at changing behavior, or if they are unsuccessful at changing both behavior and normative views. Fig. 2a and b shows how effective the positive and negative interventions are in changing subjects' moral perceptions. Fig. 2a shows the relative frequencies of subjects' normative views. Individuals have firm normative views, as exposure to different media does not alter them: There is neither a statistically significant difference between the distributions in the stigmatized work and in the positive intervention conditions (Wilcoxon rank sum, $z = -0.383$, $p = 0.702$) nor between the distributions in the stigmatized work and in the negative intervention conditions ($z = 1.391$, $p =$

¹⁸ Note that our data is discrete. Hence, technically, for a subject, who accepts the job for wage ω , but declines it for wage $\omega - 1$, all that is known is that the reservation wage lies in $[\omega - 1, \omega]$. We set the reservation wage to ω .

¹⁹ The correlation between normative view and social appropriateness is 0.45.

²⁰ Testing for a difference in distribution rather than average, we also find no significant difference between the positive intervention and stigmatized work conditions (Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, $p = 0.477$) or between the negative intervention and stigmatized work conditions (Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, $p = 0.408$). A non-parametric Wilcoxon rank sum test for treatment differences concludes similarly ($p = 0.940$ and $p = 0.526$).

Fig. 1. Labor supply in stigmatized work and neutral work conditions.
 Notes: Labor supply in the stigmatized work conditions and in the neutral work condition. For each wage in between 0 CHF and 25 CHF, the labor supply gives the share of subjects that have a reservation wage that is less or equal to the wage.

Table 2
 Effect of interventions on reservation wages.

Dependent variable: reservation wage		
	(1)	(2)
Neutral work	-8.94*** (-5.14) [-12.36, -5.51]	-8.87*** (-5.11) [-12.30, -5.45]
Stigmatized work:	1.74	1.73
Positive intervention	(0.96) [-1.83, 5.30]	(0.96) [-1.81, 5.28]
Stigmatized work:	2.15	2.16
Negative intervention	(1.22) [-1.31, 5.60]	(1.23) [-1.29, 5.60]
Constant	9.85*** (7.78) [7.36, 12.35]	
Sigma ²	102.48*** [84.28, 124.62]	100.30*** [82.49, 121.96]
N	274	274
Log-likelihood	-904.15	-900.89
Control variables	No	Yes

Notes: Coefficient estimates of tobit regressions, right-censored at 26 (n = 47). Data from neutral work condition, stigmatized work, positive intervention and negative intervention. Sigma is the standard error of the regression. Control variables: gender, age and education. t statistics in parentheses, 95 %-confidence interval in square brackets; *** = p < 0.01.

0.164).²¹ Fig. 2b depicts how appropriate subjects think others regard accepting the job. Again, there is no statistically significant difference between the distributions in the stigmatized work and in the positive intervention conditions (Wilcoxon rank sum, z = 1.169, p = 0.242) and between the distributions in the positive and in the negative intervention conditions (z = 0.801, p = 0.423). There is a small shift in the negative intervention condition: the distribution in the negative intervention condition differs from the distribution in the stigmatized work condition (z = 2.012, p = 0.044). For the complementary Krupka-Weber question of declining (rather than accepting) the job, neither condition has a statistically significant effect (see Fig. A1 in the Appendix). These findings indicate that participants have firm preexisting moral convictions regarding aiding marketing of the tobacco product, which might explain why corporate image media have no effect on labor supply.

We also ask participants who accepted stigmatized work for some wage to rate how much various reasons influenced their decision

²¹ There is a small and marginally significant difference when we compare the distributions in the positive and in the negative intervention conditions, though (Wilcoxon rank sum, z=-1.756, p=0.079).

Table 3
Relationship between reservation wages and moral perception.

Dependent variable: reservation wage						
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Normative view	-11.81*** (-3.65)		-11.03*** (-3.25)	-10.04*** (-2.96)	-8.52*** (-3.72)	-8.47*** (-3.75)
Social appropriateness		-5.39* (-1.76)	-2.15 (-0.72)	-3.82 (-1.24)	-6.09*** (-2.94)	-6.81*** (-3.27)
Constant	8.21*** (6.13)	9.37*** (6.69)	8.08*** (6.01)		8.75*** (9.42)	
Sigma ²	101.3*** (4.84)	117.1*** (4.82)	100.4*** (4.84)	94.50*** (4.84)	129.07*** (8.21)	123.9*** (8.22)
Sample	SW	SW	SW	SW	Pooled	Pooled
N	66	66	66	66	202	202
Right-censored	13	13	13	13	47	47
Log-likelihood	-212.02	-216.86	-211.76	-209.83	-645.97	-641.53
Control variables	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes

Notes: Coefficient estimates of tobit regressions, right-censored at 26. Sample: Columns (1) – (4) use data from the stigmatized work condition (SW) only, columns (5) – (6) use data from the stigmatized work, positive intervention and negative intervention conditions (Pooled). Sigma is the standard error of the regression. Independent variables: normative view measures how moral the subject rates working for the manufacturer of the cigarettes from very immoral (-1) to very moral (1); social appropriateness measures subjects’ beliefs about how appropriate others view accepting the job from very socially inappropriate (-1) to very socially appropriate (1). Control variables: gender, age, and education. t statistics in parentheses; * = $p < 0.1$; ** = $p < 0.05$; *** = $p < 0.01$.

Fig. 2. Normative perception across treatment conditions

Notes: normative view measures how moral the subject rates working for the manufacturer of the cigarettes from very immoral (-1) to very moral (1); social appropriateness measures subjects’ beliefs about how appropriate others view accepting the job from very socially inappropriate (-1) to very socially appropriate (1).

on a five-point Likert scale, from 0 = “did not at all affect my decision” to 1 = “greatly affected my decision.” One reason provided is the desire to support small tobacco farmers, a justification presented in the corporate image media. We find that participants in the positive intervention condition, who were exposed to this media, agree more strongly that this reason influenced their decision to accept stigmatized work (OLS, coefficient = 0.22, $t = 4.39$, $p < 0.001$), whereas there is no significant effect in the negative intervention condition (coefficient = -0.01, $t = -0.38$, $p = 0.704$).²² These findings suggest that corporate media provides those willing to accept stigmatized work with additional justifications for doing so, although this influence does not extend to changing broader normative perceptions.

²² We also elicit other reasons less directly related to the interventions, such as participants’ indifference to wrapping the cigarettes. The complete list is provided in the online appendix. We find no treatment effects on any of these additional reasons, with one exception: the desire to support employees of the tobacco company. Participants in the positive intervention condition agree more strongly that this reason influenced their decision to accept stigmatized work (OLS, coefficient = 0.09, $t = 2.49$, $p = 0.014$).

Relation to stated real-world employment preferences. As we have seen, behavior is not affected by the interventions. A limitation of these results is that accepting the tobacco marketing job in the laboratory differs from accepting employment at a tobacco company. To investigate this, we asked subjects how willing they are to accept a job offer at the tobacco company. A Wilcoxon rank sum test reveals no statistically significant difference in willingness to work for the tobacco company between the stigmatized work and the positive intervention condition ($z = -0.322$, $p = 0.747$). There is, however, a marginally significant difference between the stigmatized work condition and the negative intervention condition ($z = 1.870$, $p = 0.062$). Fig. A2 in the Appendix shows the distribution of willingness to work across all three conditions, indicating a potential small shift for the negative intervention but no noticeable change for the positive intervention.

Overall, we find no substantial impact of the image interventions on willingness to work for the tobacco company. Indeed, behavior in the laboratory job is closely mirrored in subjects' stated willingness to work for the tobacco company: a subject who states to be "somewhat unwilling" to work for the tobacco company is estimated to exhibit a CHF 8.70 higher reservation wage for the laboratory job than a subject who answered with "somewhat willing" (Tobit regression, $t = -5.35$, $p < 0.001$).

4. Perceptions of the corporate image media

To provide additional insights into why the corporate image media has no impact on labor supply, we conducted a survey to assess how participants perceive the videos used in the positive and negative intervention conditions, and how it impacts their view of the tobacco industry.

Design and Procedure. In November 2024, we recruited 167 participants from the joint subject pool of the University of Zurich and the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology, the same subject pool used in the initial study, to complete a short online study. Participants are randomly assigned to watch one of three videos: the video used in the positive intervention condition, produced by the tobacco company (*positive video*, $N = 54$), the video used in the negative intervention condition, produced by the American Cancer Society (*negative video*, $N = 57$), or the control video, showing landscapes ($N = 56$). After viewing the video, we elicit participants' perceptions of the video and the tobacco industry. We also elicit normative views about working in the tobacco industry and participants' willingness to work for the tobacco company, using the same measures as in the initial study. The instructions are reproduced in full in the online appendix. The survey had a median duration of 13 minutes, and participants were paid a fixed fee of 8 CHF. We pre-registered the study on AsPredicted (<https://aspredicted.org/vrtb-nnm4.pdf>).

Perceived accuracy, sincerity and persuasiveness. Participants rate the videos on sincerity, accuracy, persuasiveness, and production quality. Fig. 3 shows that less than one-third of participants find the positive video sincere (31.5 %) or accurate (31.5 %). In contrast, the negative video is perceived as sincere and accurate by a majority of participants (80.7 % and 61.4 %, respectively). These treatment differences are statistically significant for both sincerity (Wilcoxon rank-sum test; $z = 6.04$; $p < 0.001$) and accuracy ($z = 3.62$; $p < 0.001$).

Similarly, only 27.7 % of participants find the positive video convincing, compared to 71.9 % for the negative video (Wilcoxon rank-sum test; $z = 5.01$; $p < 0.001$). An OLS regression ($N = 111$, $R^2 = 0.49$) shows that perceived sincerity and accuracy largely explain such perceived persuasiveness. Specifically, a one standard deviation increase in perceived sincerity is associated with a 0.245 standard deviation increase in persuasiveness ($t = 2.52$, $p = 0.013$), while a similar increase in perceived accuracy is associated with a 0.525 standard deviation increase ($t = 6.42$, $p < 0.001$).

In summary, the positive video, produced by the tobacco company, is widely perceived as insincere, inaccurate, and unconvincing, which may contribute to its limited impact on normative views and labor supply. Conversely, the negative video is seen as accurate and sincere.

Impact on the perception of the tobacco industry. We also elicit how participants perceived the tobacco industry.²³ Fig. 4 shows the treatment effects of the positive and negative videos, relative to the control video, on these perceptions. We estimate these treatment effects based on OLS regressions and standardize all outcome measures (Appendix Table A4 gives the coefficient estimates).

The positive video highlights the benefits of tobacco cultivation for small farmers and local communities in low-income countries. Consistent with these narratives, participants exposed to the positive video are more likely to believe in these reported benefits, with effect sizes of 0.59 standard deviations ($t = 3.11$, $p = 0.002$) and 0.47 standard deviations ($t = 2.72$, $p = 0.007$), respectively. Additionally, there is an increase in the belief that the tobacco company conducts research to develop less harmful products (coefficient = 0.38, $t = 1.94$, $p = 0.055$), reflecting further content of the video. However, the video also reinforces negative views of tobacco, with participants more likely to agree that tobacco is a major global health issue (coefficient = 0.45, $t = 2.35$, $p = 0.020$). This may be a side effect of highlighting the necessity of developing less harmful tobacco products. Other narratives in the video, such as providing customers with information to make informed choices and refraining from marketing to children, do not substantially or significantly influence beliefs ($p > 0.60$).

While the positive video succeeds in changing some views about the tobacco industry, potentially providing excuses and justifications for working in tobacco, it has no impact on normative views about such work (coefficient = -0.12, $t = -0.63$, $p = 0.530$) or willingness to work for the tobacco company (coefficient = -0.10, $t = -0.54$, $p = 0.591$). This aligns with findings from the initial study, where participants exposed to the positive video justify accepting the tobacco job with narratives provided by the video but show no changes in normative views or labor supply.

²³ Appendix Fig. A3 gives the distribution of the different perceptions of the tobacco industry in the control condition.

Fig. 3. Perception of the corporate image media

Notes: We asked participants to rate their agreement with statements regarding the video's sincerity, accuracy, persuasiveness, and production quality using a five-point Likert scale, ranging from "strongly disagree" (-1) to "strongly agree" ($=1$). $N = 111$.

The negative video, produced by anti-tobacco NGOs, has no statistically significant impact on perceptions of the tobacco industry. While many outcomes were not expected to change (as they reflected narratives from the positive video), it is surprising that the negative video does not affect the perception of tobacco as a major health issue. However, the negative video influences normative views about working in the tobacco industry; participants exposed to the negative video are less likely to view such work as morally acceptable (coefficient = -0.36 , $t = -1.97$, $p = 0.051$), consistent with the video's call to "fight back" against the tobacco industry.

5. Conclusion

In this study, we first document that many people have an aversion to stigmatized work. We then study how malleable this aversion is. Specifically, we investigate whether labor supply for stigmatized work can be shifted by exposing individuals to corporate image media that includes narratives common in the debate surrounding stigmatized companies. To do so, we develop a new laboratory paradigm for studying labor supply for stigmatized work. The paradigm has three key strengths: first, the laboratory job has an external analogue (marketing of a harmful and addictive consumer product), second, the job is palpably stigmatized and, third, real-world corporate and industry image media can be used in the lab.

The stigmatized organization in our study is in terms of profit the world's biggest tobacco corporation. In the laboratory experiment, we elicit participants' reservation wages to perform a job that aids the marketing of a brand of the corporation's cigarettes. Before participants make their choices, they are randomly exposed to one of three media, a control video, a corporate image video produced by the tobacco corporation, or a video produced by the American Cancer Society, a leading opponent of the tobacco industry. While the corporate image video provides excuses for accepting employment for the tobacco industry, the video by the American Cancer Society appeals to individuals' morality to fight the tobacco industry. We also have a treatment condition in which subjects have the choice to do a similar but non-stigmatized job, which allows us to study whether there is a causal impact of work stigmatization on labor supply.

Fig. 4. Treatment effects on perception of the tobacco industry

Notes: The figure gives treatment effects of the positive video (Panel a) and the negative video (Panel b) on various outcomes, compared to the control video. We use linear regressions to estimate these effects, with all outcome measures standardized ($N = 167$). The bars represent 95 % confidence intervals (based on robust standard errors). To measure the perceptions of the tobacco industry, we asked participants to rate their agreement with different statements about the Tobacco industry and the harm of smoking using a five-point Likert scale, ranging from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree”. We used the following statements: “The tobacco industry contributes positively to the communities where it operates”, “Small farmers and their families in low-income countries benefit from cultivating tobacco”, “Smoking is one of the largest global health problems”, “The tobacco industry conducts research to develop less harmful products”, “Smoking is responsible for cancer, heart disease, lung disease, diabetes, and other serious diseases”, “The tobacco industry provides adult consumers with information to help them make informed choices” and “The tobacco industry systematically targets children as potential customers”. To measure normative views about tobacco, we asked participants to rate how immoral they would think it would be if one of their fellow students starts working for the tobacco company after finishing his/her studies on a nine-point Likert scale, ranging from “very immoral” to “very moral”. For willingness to work at the tobacco company, we asked participants how willing they would be to work for the tobacco company using a five-point Likert scale, ranging from “not willing at all” to “Very much willing”.

We find a substantial effect of work stigmatization on labor supply; the average reservation wage for the stigmatized job is more than nine times as large as for the non-stigmatized job. This depression of labor supply can be accounted for by subjects’ normative views about working for the tobacco company and their beliefs about the social appropriateness of accepting the job. Given the strong link between behavior and norms evident in the data, organizational image interventions in principle have the potential to substantially alter recruitment outcomes. However, we find that neither the corporate image video nor the anti-tobacco video succeeds in altering behavior. The data on normative views and social appropriateness suggest that this finding can be explained by participants’ firm preexisting moral convictions regarding aiding marketing of the tobacco product. In a complementary online experiment, we further demonstrate that corporate media may provide justifications for those willing to accept stigmatized work, but this influence does not extend to altering broader normative perceptions. Hence, the evidence suggests that workers’ aversion to stigmatized work is not easily affected by moral suasion or providing means for self-serving belief manipulation. Taken together, our results suggest that aversion to stigmatized work is a robust feature of preferences which causes labor supply for stigmatized work to decrease.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Appendix. Additional results

Figs. A1, A2, A3, Tables A1, A2, A3, A4.

Fig. A1. Social appropriateness of declining the job across treatment conditions

Notes: Social appropriateness measures subjects' beliefs about how appropriate others view declining the job (from -1 very socially inappropriate to 1 very socially appropriate). There is no statistically significant difference between the distribution of the stigmatized work and the positive intervention conditions (ranksum, $p = 0.872$) nor between the distribution of the stigmatized work and the negative intervention conditions (ranksum, $p = 0.106$) nor between the distribution of the positive and the negative intervention conditions (ranksum, $p = 0.092$).

Fig. A2. Willingness to work for the tobacco company

Notes: Willingness to work measures subjects' willingness to work for the tobacco company that produced the company video (from -1 Not willing at all to 1 Very much willing).

Fig. A3. Perception of the tobacco industry: distribution in control condition

Notes: To measure the perceptions of the tobacco industry, we asked participants to rate their agreement with different statements about the Tobacco industry and the harm of smoking using a five-point Likert scale, ranging from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree”. We used the following statements: “Small farmers and their families in low-income countries benefit from cultivating tobacco”, “The tobacco industry provides adult consumers with information to help them make informed choices”, “The tobacco industry conducts research to develop less harmful products”, “The tobacco industry systematically targets children as potential customers”, “Smoking is one of the largest global health problems”, “Smoking is

responsible for cancer, heart disease, lung disease, diabetes, and other serious diseases”, and “The tobacco industry contributes positively to the communities where it operates”. We focus on data in the control video condition (N = 56).

Table A1
Effect of interventions on reservation wages.

Dependent variable: reservation wage		
	(1)	(2)
Neutral work	-8.16*** (-6.85) [-10.50, -5.82]	-8.10*** (-6.65) [-10.50, -5.70]
Stigmatized work: Positive intervention	1.39 (0.80) [-2.06, 4.84]	1.39 (0.79) [-2.10, 4.88]
Stigmatized work: Negative intervention	1.91 (1.14) [-1.38, 5.20]	1.90 (1.13) [-1.42, 5.21]
Constant	9.08*** (7.90) [6.81, 11.34]	
N	274	274
R ²	0.185	0.202
Control variables	No	Yes

Notes: Coefficient estimates of liner regressions. Reservations that are right-censored at 26 (n = 47) are set to 26. Data from neutral work condition, stigmatized work, positive intervention and negative intervention. Control variables: gender, age and education. t statistics in parentheses (based on robust standard errors), 95 %-confidence interval in square brackets; *** = p < 0.01.

Table A2
Effect of interventions on declining the job for any wage.

Dependent variable: Declining job for any wage		
	(1)	(2)
Neutral work	-0.197*** (-3.99) [-0.294, -0.100]	-0.199*** (-3.98) [-0.297, -0.101]
Stigmatized work: Positive intervention	0.053 (0.72) [-0.092, 0.198]	0.050 (0.68) [-0.095, 0.194]
Stigmatized work: Negative intervention	0.025 (0.36) [-0.112, 0.163]	0.028 (0.40) [-0.109, 0.166]
Constant	0.197*** (3.99) [0.100, 0.294]	
N	274	274
R ²	0.073	0.102
Control variables	No	Yes

Notes: Coefficient estimates of linear regressions. The dependent variable is an indicator of whether the participant clicked the button to “decline to do the job for any wage.” Data from neutral work condition, stigmatized work, positive intervention and negative intervention. Control variables: gender, age and education. t statistics in parentheses (based on robust standard errors), 95 %-confidence interval in square brackets; *** = p < 0.01.

Table A3
Relationship between reservation wages and moral perception.

	Dependent variable: reservation wage			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Normative view	-7.10* (-1.57)	-8.24* (-1.80)	-6.76* (-1.65)	-6.26* (-1.57)
Social appropriateness	-9.17** (-2.19)	-7.68* (-1.75)	-7.93** (-2.11)	-10.31*** (-2.69)
Constant	9.51*** (5.55)		8.39*** (4.55)	
Sigma ²	146.9*** (4.49)	139.9*** (4.49)	136.6*** (4.90)	119.7*** (4.91)
Sample	Positive	Positive	Negative	Negative
N	64	64	72	72
Right-censored	17	17	17	17
Log-likelihood	-200.72	-198.92	-231.06	-226.40
Control variables	No	Yes	No	Yes

Notes: Coefficient estimates of tobit regressions, right-censored at 26. Sample: Columns (1) – (2) use data from the positive intervention condition, columns (3) – (4) use data from the negative interventions condition. Sigma is the standard error of the regression. Independent variables: normative view measures how moral the subject rates working for the manufacturer of the cigarettes (from -1 very immoral to 1 very moral), social appropriateness measures subjects' beliefs about how appropriate others view accepting the job (from -1 very socially inappropriate to 1 very socially appropriate). Control variables: gender, age, and education. t-statistics in parentheses; * = $p < 0.1$; ** = $p < 0.05$; *** = $p < 0.01$.

Table A4
Effect of interventions on declining the job for any wage.

Dependent variable	Positive video	Negative video
Tobacco industry supports local communities	0.587*** (3.11) [0.215, 0.959]	-0.110 (-0.61) [-0.466, 0.246]
Small farmers benefit from tobacco	0.466*** (2.72) [0.128, 0.806]	-0.131 (-0.67) [-0.515, 0.253]
Tobacco is a major global health issue	0.449** (2.35) [0.071, 0.828]	0.021 (0.11) [-0.360, 0.401]
Tobacco industry conducts research on harm reduction	0.376* (1.94) [-0.007, 0.759]	0.049 (0.25) [-0.328, 0.425]
Smoking Causes Diseases	0.207 (1.27) [-0.114, 0.528]	-0.207 (-1.06) [-0.593, 0.179]
Tobacco industry informs consumers	0.036 (0.19) [-0.338, 0.412]	-0.075 (-0.40) [-0.446, 0.296]
Tobacco industry targets children as customers	-0.092 (-0.48) [-0.473, 0.289]	0.235 (1.31) [-0.120, 0.590]
Normative views tobacco	-0.119 (-0.63) [-0.492, 0.254]	-0.364* (-1.97) [-0.730, 0.001]
Willingness to work at tobacco company	-0.105 (-0.54) [-0.489, 0.279]	-0.166 (-0.87) [-0.545, 0.213]
N	167	167

Notes: Coefficient estimates of linear regressions. The independent variables are treatment dummies for being in the positive video condition (column "Positive video") and for being in the negative video condition (column "Negative video"). The nine dependent variables (column "Dependent variable") are different perceptions of the tobacco industry, normative views about tobacco, and willingness to work for the tobacco industry. We standardized all dependent variables. To measure the perceptions of the tobacco industry, we asked participants to rate their agreement with different statements about the Tobacco industry and the harm of smoking using a five-point Likert scale, ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree". We used the following statements: "The tobacco industry contributes positively to the communities where it operates", "Small farmers and their families in low-income countries benefit from cultivating tobacco", "Smoking is one of the largest global health problems", "The tobacco industry conducts research to develop less harmful products", "Smoking is responsible for cancer, heart disease, lung disease, diabetes, and other serious diseases", "The tobacco industry provides adult consumers with information to help them make informed choices" and "The tobacco industry systematically targets children as potential customers". To measure normative views about tobacco, we asked participants to rate how immoral they would think it would be if one of their fellow students starts working for the tobacco company after finishing his/her studies on a nine-point Likert scale, ranging from "very immoral" to "very moral". For willingness to work at the tobacco company, we asked participants

how willing they would be to work for the tobacco company using a five-point Likert scale, ranging from “not willing at all” to “Very much willing”. *t* statistics in parentheses (based on robust standard errors), 95 %-confidence interval in square brackets; * = $p < 0.1$, ** = $p < 0.05$, *** = $p < 0.01$.

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